

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NDI****FIRST NAME: RICHARD****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

THE ART OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) **INTRODUCTION**

The study material for technical academic writing at Euclid University provides a review of expectations for graduate-level academic writing. The course material is a toolkit that outlines the basics ethics of academic writing and is intended to help students in the successful completion of their program (EUCLID 2015, 2). I find the detail information on essay writing useful, even though the basic steps in easy writing are issues I have dealt with in my past graduate level studies.

2) **PERIOD 1 COURSEPACK**

The study material for the course “International Academic Writing” is a document that presents an introduction to the basics of academic writing. The first five pages are material retrieved from an online source: <http://www.lc.unsw.edu.au> and present the basics of a good essay. References are listed at the bottom of the 5th page, this should have appeared on a separate page. However, the pages are not numbered and the study material it is not a single document with a logical flow and publication date. The document proceeds on what is a PowerPoint presentation with advice on what makes an excellent paper and on the dangers of plagiarism and then footnote referencing part 1 and 2. The “Crib Sheet” for the CMS (Chicago Manual Style) provides useful guidance on the style of writing.

The coursepack for period one (1) is a document of 83 pages that presents a sequence of academic writing technics for a good paper. The material informs on the ethics

of plagiarism and how the Euclid University takes the issue seriously, it emphasizes that the writer should do all he can to avoid plagiarism because it is wrong and unethical in academic writing and goes with serious consequences (EUCLID 2015, 8-10). I find the explanations on when to give credit to an author's idea useful. This could be through citations or paraphrasing, while direct quotations are used for accuracy and impact. In order for the student's work to be original, the overuse of quotations should be avoided, though the student can paraphrase by restating the author's idea in their own words.

The examples of what is acceptable and unacceptable paraphrasing are given to help the student's understanding. I was interested to know from the study material when not to cite in the course of writing, this is when the formation you are referring to is well known and can be tracked easily. In this case, the student does not need a full citation but the page number (EUCLID 2015, 29-31). The signal phrases which are used to introduce a quotation or paraphrase is what I often do, the explanation did clarify the matter.

3) TWO MAJOR WRITING STYLES

EUCLID University has proposed two major styles of academic writing, while the response paper is to be written in the American Psychological Association (APA) style, the student's major paper is to follow the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) which is referenced by the surname of its author Kate Turabian (EUCLID 2015, 66). Personally, I used the Turabian style during my master's degree in Environmental Governance at the United Nations (UN) University, Tokyo 2013 and for my Master of Arts in Development Studies, 2004 at the International Institute of Social Studies, Netherlands. This style will, therefore, guide my work at EUCLID. I am familiar with the CMS in terms of organizing citations, bibliography and in the use of both in-text and footnotes at the bottom of the page. I have not used the APA for written work before and will be keen to learn the difference between the two major styles during this program.

Although, we may be asked to use different citation style in different setting, two are the most used form in academic writing, both outlined in the Turabian manual: notes-bibliography style and author-date style (Turabian 2013, 87-88).

The two styles can be briefly being summarized as follow:

- 1) the notes-bibliography style, involves the use of:
 - *in-text citation* consecutively numbered and marked in the text, which refer the reader to footnotes that acknowledge the source of information, and
 - *end-text citation* with the bibliography at the end of the document, which provides full details of all sources cited and consulted, by the writer.
- 2) While the author-date style use:
 - *text citations*, which brief identifying information within the text by the author's last name and the publication year of the work cited. No punctuation

is used between the name and the date, and for direct quotations the page number is also included, and

- *a reference list* of sources used at the end of the document, which provides full bibliographic information.

The samples of corrections provided from a number of written papers were useful, the corrections brought to the fore the importance of bridges sentences. In order for a writer to achieve a logical, he should use transition words such as “however,” “nevertheless,” “moreover,” “furthermore,” and also organize your paper in headings, and subheadings and not that this depends on the length of the paper.

The Crib Sheet by Dr. Abel Scribe presents the Chicago Style of formatting papers and books as documented in the CMS, 2003 and in Kate Turabian’s “Manual for Writers” published by the University of Chicago Press, 1996. (EUCLID 2015, 66). A style guide means your approach to writing as a writer, consequently, there is a need to ensure consistency in the course of your work.

I learned that creative writing is not the ability to adhere to a standard English writing style but technical writers would follow certain rules and features of writing in a particular field base on previous publications. The Crib Sheet makes it clear that the writer’s style is not only about grammar, punctuation, and vocabulary but also about the readership, depth, and treatment of the subject matter, structure as well as the use of accepted terminology.

4) CONCLUSION

I have been involved in research at the master’s degree level in the past and, therefore, very familiar with academic writing ethics. As a social scientist with 2 Master’s degrees from renowned institutions as the UN University, I am very conversant with both quantitative and qualitative research methods and the importance of adhering to EUCLID style of writing. My academic writing experience includes two (2) master’s thesis, an MSc research thesis at the UN University that contained 60 pages including bibliography. The coursepack served as a refresher for me and I enjoyed reading the material for its quality and authenticity.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 1*. Sourced from: <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.